

HISTORY, PRESENT AND FUTURE OF TEA INDUSTRY IN INDIA

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Introduction

The tea plant (*Camellia sinensis* L.O. Kuntze $2n=2x=30$) is the oldest plant used to prepare non-alcoholic caffeinated hot drinks. It has its origin from South-West China. India is the second largest producer of tea globally. Indian tea is one of the finest in the world due to strong geographical indications, heavy investment in tea processing units, continuous innovation, augmented product mix and strategic market expansion.

History of Tea Industry in India

Robert Bruce first saw some patches of tea plants growing in the hills near the Ahome Dynasty during his official tour in 1823. Rangpur and he was the true discoverer of the native Assam tea plants (Ukers, 1935). Later his brother C.A. Bruce took the initiative to confirm the discovery of the tea plant by the Government Botanical Garden in Kolkata. He was later honored with a medal by the English Society of Arts through the Agricultural and Horticultural Society of Bengal for the discovery of the Assam tea plant (Barua, 1989).

Lord William Bentinck, Governor-General of the British Empire of India, appointed a Tea Committee in 1834 to study the possibility of commercial tea cultivation in the country. The committee reported that the northeastern region could be the most suitable location for tea plantations. The first tea samples sent to Calcutta in 1836 and on January 10, 1889 eight cases of Assam tea were auctioned for the first time and Assam tea was recognized as a beverage. This marked the beginning around the world as plant material and presently more tea is prepared from the *assamica* type plant.

The Assam Company was the first private tea company, established in 1839. Many more were soon added. Later, by 1856, many tea plantations were established in the hill districts of Darjeeling in West Bengal. In 1840 tea plantations with Sinensis bushes were planted in Dehradun and Kangra in the western Himalayas. The age of the Indian tea industry is estimated at around 170 years.

Scientific Cultivation of Tea

Earlier seed was the only source of propagation; therefore, *jat* populations of unknown parents produced a wide range of genetic variation and consequent inconsistencies in their performance. This led to the establishment of the Tocklai Experimental Station by the Indian Tea Research Association in 1930 and the establishment of the Tea Research Foundation by the United Planters Association of Southern India in 1963. Germplasms were collected based on the trait-specific phenotypic traits, promising plants selected from a heterogeneous *jat* population and from wild tea fields were characterized and conserved along with non-tea camellia species. The technique of vegetative propagation was standardized in 1955, thus providing scope for the development of improved clonal varieties and biclonal seed varieties through hybridization. Polyploid breeding triploids, tetraploids and aneuploids were also selected, cloned and provided for planting (Bezbaruah, 1974; Satyanarayana and Sharma, 1991).

Present Status of Tea Industry in India

Tea production from North Indian states such as Assam (672.14 Mkg), West Bengal (408.73 Mkg) and other states (32.17 Mkg) total 1113.04 Mkg of tea production. While the South Indian states such as Tamil Nadu (165.88 Mkg), Kerala (60.36 Mkg), Karnataka (5.12 Mkg) total 231.36 Mkg of tea production. The total Indian tea production for 2021-22 is 1344.40 Mkg.

In the north Indian states, there are 157,290 tea plantations covering an area of 535,629.04 hectares; while the South Indian States have 54504 tea plantations with an estimated area of 100928.03 hectares.

India is the fourth largest global tea export with a volume of 196.54 MKg; while the country like Kenya, China and Sri Lanka are the top three exporting countries for tea. Russia is the largest importer. Indian tea is auctioned at US\$2.35/kg, while Sri Lankan tea is auctioned at a higher price of US\$3.11/kg (ITC Annual Bulletin of Statistics, 2022).

India is the 32nd largest tea importer in the world, mainly from Nepal, Kenya, Vietnam, Sri Lanka and Iran due to high demand for domestic tea consumption.

Fig 1: Tea Growing Region of India

Future Tea Industry in India

Due to tight linkage, it is not possible to eliminate some unwanted traits or combine some desired traits in the offspring. Therefore, the new technologies developed through biotechnological research, such as tissue culture technology, protoplast technology, gene transfer technology, marker-assisted selection, are means for developing plants with desired properties.

Conclusion

The tea industry in India has an ever-changing consumer taste perception and a major challenge for breeders when it comes to plant material that will satisfies a cross-section of consumers with different taste perceptions. The effects of global climate change have increased the likelihood of biotic and abiotic stress, so planting material needs to fight stress, therefore the dynamics of breeding stress-tolerant planting material need to be increased. Due to the increase in input costs, low input response plant materials will be a demand for the tea industry in India.

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